

A privacy-preserving infrastructure for multimodal mobility sensing in environmental social research

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ABSTRACT

Understanding how individuals interact with their environment is central to environmental social research, yet collecting detailed behavioral data raises significant privacy concerns. We present a privacy-by-design infrastructure for multimodal mobility sensing that combines passive smartphone-based data collection with survey inputs and external environmental datasets. The system processes sensitive location information directly on participants' devices using a local-first processing model, transmitting only spatially and temporally aggregated records to prevent the reconstruction of individual trajectories. The infrastructure was validated through multiple data collection campaigns in two Living Labs in Switzerland (in Fribourg and Winterthur) between September 2024 and February 2026, involving 112 participants and over 37,000 recorded trips. Using this dataset, we describe the mobility characteristics of the study population and demonstrate the system's analytical utility by examining how walking behavior varies with temperature conditions. The results indicate that higher temperatures are associated with a reduced share of walking within trips that remain feasible to perform on foot. These findings illustrate how privacy-aware sensing infrastructures can support longitudinal behavioral research while maintaining strict data protection standards across diverse urban and functional contexts.

Introduction

Understanding how individuals interact with their physical and social environment is central to environmental social sciences. Human mobility patterns, energy use, and lifestyle choices collectively shape environmental impacts and determine the effectiveness of interventions aimed at promoting sustainable behavior¹⁻³. These behavioral dimensions are interconnected: changes in one domain may reinforce or counteract behaviors in others, producing spillover effects⁴. Capturing such dynamics that span over different dimensions requires measurement infrastructures that extend beyond single indicators or isolated behavioral contexts.

Existing approaches to assess environmentally relevant behavior often focus on one dimension at a time^{5,6}. More multidimensional analyses, such as carbon footprint calculators^{7,8} or expenditure-based assessments⁹, provide aggregate estimates but rely heavily on self-reported or financial data, offer limited temporal resolution, and do not allow continuous behavioral monitoring across contexts. Intervention studies frequently target specific behaviors, such as transport mode choice^{10,11} or residential energy use¹², without systematically observing behavioral variation across other domains. While survey-based instruments allow multidimensional assessment, they require sustained participant engagement and are vulnerable to recall bias.

In parallel, advances in smartphone sensing have enabled passive collection of high-resolution mobility data^{13,14}. However, many available mobility tracking systems rely on centralized processing of raw location traces¹⁵, allowing reconstruction of trajectories and frequently visited locations^{16,17}. Such approaches pose substantial privacy risks, as mobility traces can enable re-identification even after pseudonymization¹⁸, potentially undermining participant trust and long-term engagement. Moreover, mobility data are rarely integrated with qualitative behavioral indicators or with additional sensing sources such as building-level measurements, limiting their usefulness for comprehensive environmental social analysis.

To address these limitations, we developed a reusable privacy-preserving infrastructure for multimodal behavioral data collection that integrates passive mobility sensing, survey-based assessments, and optional fixed sensor data (e.g., building sensors) within a unified architecture. The system is designed around three core principles: (i) privacy-by-design on-device processing of sensitive location data, (ii) irreversible spatial and temporal aggregation prior to transmission, and (iii) modular integration of heterogeneous data streams to enable multidimensional behavioral modeling.

Our framework facilitates high-resolution longitudinal analysis of the interaction of humans with their environment while optimizing the tradeoff between granular, automated mobility sensing and participant anonymity. To illustrate the analytical capabilities of the system, we present two example analyses based on the collected dataset: descriptive mobility characteristics of the study population and an exploration of how walking behavior varies with temperature conditions. Together, these

examples demonstrate how privacy-aware mobility sensing infrastructures can support environmental social research while maintaining strict data protection standards.

Results

This section first presents the architecture of the proposed mobility sensing infrastructure and the design of the mobile application used for data collection. We then illustrate the analytical capabilities of the system through descriptive analyses of the collected mobility dataset and an exploration of temperature-related variation in walking behavior.

System architecture and mobility detection

Overall system architecture

The proposed infrastructure integrates passive smartphone-based mobility sensing, survey-based self-reports, and environmental data sources within a unified privacy-preserving framework (Figure 1). The system follows a decentralized architecture in which sensitive raw data are processed locally on participants' devices and only aggregated, anonymized representations are transmitted to a secure server for research purposes.

(a) Privacy-preserving data processing and integration architecture

(b) SWICE mobile application interface: eco-feedback and correction of detected mode of transport

Figure 1. Schematic of the overall multimodal data collection infrastructure including mobility, survey, and external sensor data (a). This is complemented by the SWICE application interface (b), that serves as the personal data collection and anonymization portal as well as being the main point of contact between experimenters and participants.

The architecture consists of three main components: (i) a data integration layer that harmonizes mobility, survey, and external sensor data (Figure 1a), (ii) a mobile application that serves as the personal data collection (i.e., individual mobility patterns and survey responses) and anonymization portal, acting as the primary point of contact between researchers and participants (Figure 1b), and (iii) a secure research server for aggregate analysis and the dissemination of open research data. This modular design allows multidimensional behavioral modeling while maintaining strict data minimization and privacy preservation principles through on-device processing and spatiotemporal aggregation.

Raw location traces never leave the participant's device. Instead, mobility events are transformed into spatially and temporally aggregated representations prior to transmission. This separation between sensitive raw data and research-ready data substantially reduces re-identification risks while preserving analytical utility.

Mobility detection app

The mobile application (named SWICE), available for Android and iOS platforms, leverages native operating system activity recognition services combined with GPS-based location signals and derived movement features. Transport mode inference follows a hybrid approach: initial activity classifications provided by the operating system are refined using contextual heuristics.

These heuristics include speed thresholds for walking and cycling, detection of high-speed movement consistent with air travel, proximity to transport infrastructure for classification of train, subway and cable car trips, and spatiotemporal alignment with routes and timetables for bus and tram. This rule-based refinement increases precision and robustness while avoiding centralized processing of raw trajectories and using a limited amount of resources on the participant's smartphone.

All raw GPS data are stored and processed locally on the device. For each detected movement occurrence, only an aggregated record is exported to the server. Each record contains: (i) the pseudonym of the participant whose device registered the movement, (ii) start and end timestamps, (iii) start and end locations aggregated to geohashes¹⁹ with 6 characters ("geohash-6", cells with an average size of $1.22\text{ km} \times 0.61\text{ km}$), (iv) total distance traveled, (v) inferred transport mode before and after

optional user correction, and (vi) estimated CO₂ equivalent (CO₂e) emissions of the trip. The path between start and end locations is not stored.

To enable aggregate analysis of space and route usage while preventing accurate trajectory reconstruction, additional location samples are transmitted disjointed from the movement records. These samples are spatially aggregated to 8-character geohashes (“geohash-8”, cells with an average size of 38.2 m × 19.1 m), temporally reduced to hour-level intervals, day of the week, and month, and transmitted as independent, non-linked records. They are not linked to participant identifiers and are not temporally ordered nor linked, preventing reconstruction of individual mobility paths. Additionally, the records inside the initial and final geohash (length 6) of the corresponding movement record are discarded prior to transmission, to avoid producing hotspots around people’s regularly visited locations (e.g., exact home or work coordinates).

The application includes a user-facing dashboard that allows participants to visualize their aggregated mobility patterns and estimated CO₂e emissions associated with recorded trips, based on mode-specific emission factors. Users can manually correct inferred transport modes and specify more detailed subcategories (e.g., distinguishing conventional bicycles from electric bicycles). For recurring transport types, users may define a preferred default subtype, which is automatically applied to subsequent detections within the broader category. These features were designed to enhance transparency, improve data quality through user feedback, and support sustained engagement and user retention during longitudinal deployments.

The application was deployed starting September 2024 in several data collection campaigns in two regions in Switzerland, involving 112 participants with at least one recorded movement, of whom 62 had recorded at least 100 movements by February 2026. Descriptive analyses of detected transport modes and speed distributions indicate behaviorally plausible patterns, supporting the suitability of the developed hybrid detection approach for aggregate mobility analysis. In one deployment campaign, participants were additionally surveyed regarding perceived detection accuracy and battery consumption. Responses indicated that the application was generally perceived as accurate and had only a limited impact on battery consumption.

Integration of environmental and fixed sensing data

The infrastructure is designed to facilitate the harmonization of mobility records with heterogeneous data streams through compatible spatial and temporal indexing. As illustrated in Figure 1a, the architecture supports the inclusion of both external environmental datasets, such as hourly meteorological records from the Open-Meteo API, and localized fixed sensing sources, including building-level sensors for indoor climate and occupancy.

Because mobility data are spatially coarsened to geohash-6 cells and temporally reduced to hourly intervals prior to transmission, the integration of these diverse variables does not require access to precise trajectories or exact timestamps. Instead, the standardized format of the exported records allows for straightforward spatiotemporal joins with external datasets during post-processing. This “interoperable-by-design” approach ensures that adding granular environmental or building-level context does not increase re-identification risks, as the alignment occurs strictly at the aggregate level. Consequently, the architecture enables multidimensional analyses of how ambient and indoor environments influence behavioral choices while maintaining a robust separation between sensitive raw sensor traces and research-ready datasets.

Finally, an additional anonymization layer is applied when exporting these integrated datasets for research dissemination. Prior to release, potentially sensitive variables, including participant pseudonyms and building identifiers, are transformed using a one-way hashing function to prevent reverse identification while preserving the internal consistency of the longitudinal records.

Analyses of collected data

To illustrate the utility of the proposed infrastructure, we examine several descriptive and exploratory assessments of the collected dataset. These include an overview of the study population’s mobility characteristics and a detailed analysis of walking behavior under varying temperature conditions. While the system architecture is designed for multidimensional integration, including the capacity to incorporate localized fixed sensing sources, the following analyses focus on the integration of mobility records with external meteorological data as a proof-of-concept for the system’s spatiotemporal join capabilities.

The analyses presented in this section are based on data collected between September 2024 and February 2026 during several data collection campaigns conducted in two regions of Switzerland. The dataset includes 112 participants with at least one recorded movement, of whom 62 recorded more than 100 movements during the observation period, resulting in a dataset of 40,724 recorded movements, of which 37,027 completely in Switzerland.

Descriptive mobility characteristics

To provide an overview of the mobility data captured by the proposed infrastructure, we examine several descriptive characteristics of the recorded dataset. These include the distribution of detected transport modes, their spatial relationship with transportation infrastructure, and temporal patterns of movements during weekdays and weekends. The 37,027 records with both start and end locations in Switzerland were used for this purpose to simplify comparisons with Swiss mobility statistics and ensure consistent spatial reference with the transportation infrastructure datasets used in the analysis.

Figure 2. Distance-based modal split of mobility recorded in the study dataset compared with Swiss national mobility statistics. Shares in the study dataset were computed using the total distance traveled per transport mode across all detected trips. Swiss statistics are based on person-kilometers traveled per mode (reference year 2023)²⁰.

Figure 2 illustrates the distance-based modal split of recorded mobility in the study dataset and compares it with reference mobility statistics for Switzerland. Modal shares in the collected dataset were computed using the total distance traveled per transport mode across all detected trips. In the recorded data (Figure 2a), rail travel represents the largest share of traveled distance (58.3%), followed by private motorized road transport (28.3%), walking and cycling (9.6%), and bus and tram services (3.7%).

Although the modal distribution differs from national mobility statistics²⁰, where private road transport typically represents the dominant share of traveled distance, these differences are consistent with the characteristics of the participant sample and the geographic context of the data collection campaigns. According to surveys conducted through the mobile application, 47% of participants reported having access to at least one car in their household, compared with 78% of households in Switzerland in 2021²¹. Similarly, only 5% of participants reported access to two or more cars, compared with 29% nationally. Reduced car availability in the study sample contributes to the higher relative share of rail-based mobility observed in the dataset. This high share of rail travel is consistent with the urban, transit-oriented nature of the two Living Lab recruitment sites (Fribourg and Winterthur).

Within public transport trips (Figure 2b), rail-based movements represent the majority of recorded distances (94.1%), followed by bus (5.1%) and tram (0.8%). While these proportions differ from national statistics, they are influenced by the transport infrastructures available in the two study regions and the longer distances typically associated with rail travel. Overall, the observed modal distributions reflect mobility patterns that are consistent with the characteristics of the study regions and participant sample.

Figure 3. Temporal distribution of recorded trips across the week.

Temporal patterns of recorded movements provide additional insight into the structure of the collected dataset. Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of detected trips across days of the week and hours of the day. The heatmap reveals clear weekday mobility peaks during the morning (7:00-9:00) and evening hours (17:00-19:00), corresponding to typical commuting periods in Switzerland¹⁵. During weekends, movements are more evenly distributed throughout the day, with higher activity observed around mid-day.

To further examine the spatial consistency of detected transport modes, we compared the start and end locations of trips classified as public transport with the locations of corresponding stations and stops extracted from OpenStreetMap. For each trip, the center coordinates of the origin and destination geohashes were compared with nearby infrastructure, and a trip was

considered spatially consistent if a station or stop of the corresponding mode was located within a radius of 700 m, which approximately corresponds to half the diagonal of a geohash-6 cell at Switzerland’s coordinates.

Across the 9,898 trips classified as rail, bus, or tram travel, 96.3% of origins and 96.9% of destinations fall within this distance of the relevant infrastructure, while 93.8% of trips have both their origin and destination located within this range. Mode-specific results show particularly strong spatial consistency for bus and tram trips, where fewer than 2% of trips lack nearby stops. Rail trips exhibit slightly larger distances to stations (6.2% of origins and 5.7% of destinations beyond the threshold), which likely reflects typical access and egress patterns, such as walking or using local transport to reach railway stations, as well as small timing offsets in the detection of mode transitions. For instance, at typical rail speeds of 120 km/h, a one-minute delay in activity state transition results in a spatial offset of 2 km, which exceeds the diagonal length of the geohash-6 cells used for aggregation.

Importantly, this analysis is performed using spatially aggregated trip endpoints rather than precise trajectories. The results therefore illustrate that meaningful spatial analyses of mobility behavior remain possible even when location data are coarsened to preserve participant privacy. The strong correspondence between detected trips and transportation infrastructure indicates that the collected data provide a reliable representation of participants’ travel behavior at the spatial resolution considered in this study.

Temperature-related variation in walking within walkable trips

To illustrate how the proposed infrastructure enables the integration of mobility records with external environmental datasets, we examine how walking behavior varies with ambient temperature. As described in the Methods, for each mobility record, the corresponding hourly maximum temperatures were obtained based on the spatial location of the start and end trip observations. Because mobility locations are spatially aggregated prior to transmission, this integration with external environmental data can be performed without requiring access to precise individual trajectories.

To characterize daily heat exposure, we computed the maximum daily temperature experienced across all locations visited by a participant as an indicator of their general perceived thermal environment. The analysis focuses on movements recorded during the summer months (June to September), when temperature variations are most relevant for outdoor mobility choices. To isolate the effect of temperature on walking behavior, the analysis was restricted to “walkable” trips, following established methodologies for active travel assessment²². We defined this threshold at 1500 m, representing the 90th percentile of all detected walking trip lengths in the dataset. This ensures that the analysis focuses on movements where walking remains a viable and frequent alternative to other types of transport.

For each participant-day, we modeled the share of walking duration relative to the total duration of trips under the 1.500 m threshold. We employed a binomial generalized linear model (GLM) with a logit link, using cluster-robust standard errors to account for the nested structure of the longitudinal data (multiple observations per participant). The analysis includes 1,751 participant-day observations from the summer period. The model indicates a significant negative association between daily maximum temperature and the share of walking within walkable trips ($\beta = -0.025$, $p = 0.026$), corresponding to an approximate 2–3% decrease in the odds of walking for each additional degree Celsius.

Figure 4. Relationship between daily maximum temperature and the share of walking within walkable trips. The solid line represents the predicted walking share for the main walkability threshold (1.500 m), with the shaded area indicating the 95% confidence interval. Thin lines show the corresponding predictions for alternative thresholds of 1.000 m and 2.000 m. Points indicate observed walking ratios aggregated into 2 °C temperature bins.

To assess the robustness of this finding, the analysis was repeated using alternative walkability thresholds of 1.000 m and 2.000 m, resulting in 1,633 and 1,824 participant-day observations respectively. The estimated temperature effect remains consistent across these specifications ($\beta \approx -0.026$, $p < 0.05$ in both cases), indicating that the observed relationship is not sensitive to the precise definition of walkable trips. Figure 4 illustrates the predicted walking share as a function of temperature for the main threshold, together with empirical observations and the corresponding confidence interval.

Overall, the decrease in walking within trips that remain feasible to perform on foot suggests a temperature-related shift in mobility behavior away from walking under warmer conditions. This pattern is consistent with a partial shift toward other transport options when temperatures increase during warm months²³.

Discussion

The results presented in this study illustrate how privacy-preserving mobility sensing infrastructures can support behavioral research while minimizing risks related to personal data collection. By processing sensitive location information directly on participants' devices and transmitting only spatially aggregated mobility records, the proposed system enables the collection of longitudinal mobility datasets without storing reconstructable trajectories. This approach directly addresses the “privacy paradox” in mobility research, where the high utility of GPS data is often competing with the necessity of participant anonymity¹⁸.

The descriptive analyses of the collected dataset show mobility patterns that, while distinct from national averages, are consistent with the specific contexts of the study. The high share of rail travel observed deviates significantly from the private-vehicle dominance typically seen in Swiss national statistics²⁰, yet aligns with the transit-oriented nature of the two Living Lab recruitment sites, as shown by the survey results. This suggests that the infrastructure effectively captures the mobility characteristics of urban districts, though it also underscores the influence of recruitment bias inherent to the Living Lab methodology.

The integration of mobility records with external environmental data further illustrates the potential of the infrastructure for cross-domain research. The observed decrease in the walking share during warmer conditions suggests that even within walkable distances, thermal conditions play a role in mode choice. While the observational nature of the dataset does not allow for causal interpretation, these results demonstrate how privacy-aware sensing can be used to monitor behavioral responses to climate variables, consistent with established literature on thermal comfort and active travel²³.

Several limitations must be acknowledged. The current analysis relies on a relatively small, non-representative sample of active users within urban Swiss contexts, which limits the generalizability of the findings to rural or less transit-dense regions. Furthermore, the reliance on user-corrected heuristics for mode inference, while reducing server-side computational load, introduces potential variations in data quality across different smartphone models and operating systems. Future work will focus on expanding the diversity of the participant pool and conducting longitudinal analyses to observe how mobility patterns evolve in response to seasonal changes and urban interventions.

Overall, the proposed architecture provides a flexible framework for studying environmentally relevant behavior while maintaining strict privacy guarantees. This study establishes a validated baseline within and beyond the SWICE consortium to conduct longitudinal research into the interactions between human mobility, building-level energy use, and climate adaptation strategies.

Methods

Ethical approval and data protection

The research infrastructure and data collection protocols, including the SWICE mobile application and associated environmental sensing, were reviewed and approved by the Internal Review Board of the Department of Psychology at the University of Fribourg (Decision 2023-854 R1). Notably, this approval was granted for a generalized framework for multiple behavioral experiments rather than a single study. This allows for the longitudinal collection of mobility and environmental data across diverse research contexts while ensuring compliance with the Swiss Federal Act on Data Protection. The infrastructure's “privacy-by-design” principles are further aligned with the European General Data Protection Regulation standards, facilitating future cross-border research collaborations and data interoperability.

The Board's approval specifically validates the system's privacy-by-design approach, which follows a strict local-first processing model for raw location data. High-resolution GPS coordinates are stored on the participant's smartphone only for the duration required to complete transport mode inference and spatial aggregation. Once the transformation into geohash-6 and geohash-8 records is finalized and the resulting data is successfully transmitted to the research server, all corresponding raw location traces are permanently erased from the local storage. This ensures that no long-term trajectory history is maintained on the device or the server. No unique hardware identifiers or biometric data are collected or transmitted, except for the smartphone model and operating system version, mainly for debugging purposes. This irreversible spatial and temporal aggregation prior

to transmission substantially mitigates re-identification risks while maintaining the granular utility required for behavioral analysis.

Data collection and study population

Data were collected through several recruitment campaigns in Switzerland between September 2024 and February 2026. Participants were recruited within two distinct Living Lab contexts: the Smart Living Lab in Fribourg (workplace-focused) and Lokstadt in Winterthur (residential-focused). Eligibility criteria included residency in Switzerland, ownership of a compatible smartphone (Android 8.1+ or iOS 16+), and being at least 18 years old.

A total of 112 participants successfully registered at least one movement record. To ensure data quality for behavioral analysis, we identified a subset of 62 active users who recorded more than 100 movement events during the observation period. The resulting dataset comprises 40,724 movement records, 37,027 of which fully in Switzerland, which serve as the basis for the descriptive and exploratory analyses presented in this report.

Environmental data integration

External meteorological data were integrated by querying the Open-Meteo historical API using the geohash-6 centroids of all recorded trip endpoints. For each location visited by a participant, hourly maximum temperature values were retrieved for the entire duration of the corresponding day. This approach allows for the correlation of environmental conditions with mobility behavior without requiring access to high-precision timestamps or exact user coordinates, thereby maintaining the system's privacy-by-design standards.

To characterize the general daily heat exposure for each participant, we derived a “daily maximum perceived temperature” metric. This was calculated by taking the maximum hourly temperature across all geohash locations visited by an individual within a 24-hour period. By considering the maximum temperature across all visited sites, rather than only the temperature at the specific moment of travel, this metric acts as a proxy for the general ambient heat intensity experienced by the participant throughout the day. This longitudinal environmental mapping enables the analysis of how sustained daily heat exposure influences subsequent transport mode choices, such as the shift from walking to motorized transport.

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Author Contributions

M.C. developed the mobile application, performed the data analysis, and prepared the initial manuscript draft. J.N. supervised the study and provided conceptual feedback. Both authors co-designed the system architecture and reviewed the manuscript.

Data availability statement

The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.